
Priority Directions for Further Development of the Economy by Improving Operations with Securities in Joint-Stock Companies

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Abstract: The article examines the priority directions of further development of the economy by improving operations with securities in joint-stock companies. The theoretical foundations of the functioning of the securities market, the dynamics of its development, the structure of trading and the participation of joint-stock companies in the issue and turnover of securities are analyzed. Special attention is paid to the problems of low liquidity, legal barriers and protection of investors improving securities transactions, including regulatory reforms, development of financial instruments and digitalization. The prospects for the development of the market and its impact on the country's economy are considered.

Keywords: securities market, joint-stock companies, issue of shares, stock market, investments, corporate governance, liquidity, legal barriers, investor protection.

Introduction

The development of the stock market is one of the key factors of economic growth and financial stability of the country. Securities transactions in joint-stock companies (JSCs) play a significant role in attracting investments, increasing the capitalization of companies and ensuring liquidity in the market. In the context of digitalization and integration into the global economy, improving the mechanisms for the circulation of securities in joint-stock companies is becoming a priority area of economic policy.

In Uzbekistan, the securities market is actively developing, but a number of problems remain that impede its effective functioning. In particular, there is a low liquidity of the stock market, a limited range of investment instruments, insufficient transparency of operations, as well as weak involvement of joint-stock companies in public offering mechanisms (IPO and SPO). In addition, a significant part of securities transactions is carried out in the unorganized market, which reduces the investment attractiveness of the country.

Improving securities transactions in JSCs requires a comprehensive approach, including reforming the legislative framework, introducing international regulatory standards, developing financial infrastructure and digital technologies. The creation of favorable conditions for the issuance and circulation of securities will not only increase the capitalization of companies, but also strengthen the integration of Uzbekistan into international financial markets.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the current state of the securities market in the JSC of Uzbekistan, to identify the main problems and to propose priority areas for its further development. To achieve this goal, the theoretical foundations of the stock market functioning will be considered, the current state of securities transactions in joint-stock companies will be analyzed, and recommendations for their improvement will be formulated.

Materials.

Theoretical Foundations of the Functioning of the Securities Market in JSCs

The securities market is an important component of the financial system, ensuring effective redistribution of capital and contributing to economic development. Securities issued by joint-stock companies play a key role in the process of mobilizing financial resources and increasing liquidity in the market. This part of the article considers the main theoretical approaches to the functioning of the stock market, as well as the role of joint-stock companies in the process of issuing and circulating securities.

Concept and classification of securities. Securities are financial instruments that can be traded on the market and provide their owners with the right to receive income or fulfill certain obligations. In theory, there are several types of securities: shares, bonds, deposits, options and others.

Shares are equity securities that confirm the right of their owners to participate in the management of a joint-stock company, as well as to receive a share of profits in the form of dividends. Bonds, in turn, are debt securities that provide the right to receive a fixed income (interest) in exchange for borrowed funds.

By issuing shares, joint-stock companies attract capital for the implementation of their investment projects, expansion of production activities and ensuring financial stability.

The role of joint-stock companies in the securities market. Joint-stock companies are the main issuers of securities on the stock market. The issue of shares allows companies to attract funds from investors to develop and strengthen their positions in the market. In turn, the stock market provides joint-stock companies with the opportunity to increase their capitalization, improve liquidity and increase investment attractiveness.

The process of issuing shares by a joint-stock company includes several stages. At the initial stage, the company develops the terms of the issue, develops a prospectus, conducts a public offering of shares and lists on the stock exchange. After that, the shares begin to circulate on the market, and investors can buy and sell them.

One of the main tasks of joint-stock companies is to ensure the transparency of securities transactions, protect the rights of investors and comply with corporate norms and standards. In Uzbekistan, the regulation of the stock market and the activities of joint-stock companies is largely determined by the legal framework aimed at developing the financial infrastructure and strengthening investor confidence.

The impact of the stock market on the economy. The stock market has a significant impact on the country's economy. It contributes to the effective redistribution of capital, providing access to investment resources for enterprises, which stimulates their growth and development.

The securities market also affects other segments of the financial system, such as banks, insurance companies, and pension funds, contributing to improved liquidity of these institutions. The securities market can become an important source of financing for large infrastructure projects and public investment, as demonstrated by world practices.

However, in order for the stock market to effectively perform its functions, it is necessary to create an appropriate legislative and institutional infrastructure. According to the researchers, an important aspect of the development of the securities market is the creation of mechanisms to protect the rights of investors, ensure the transparency of trading and establish clear rules for the issuance and circulation of securities.

Literature review

The development of the securities market is the subject of research by many economists, since it plays an important role in the formation of the investment climate and the redistribution of capital. In the works of such authors as Ibodullaev A.A. and Narziev O.S., the need to modernize the organized market and adapt it to international standards is emphasized [4]. Studies show that the

unorganized market in Uzbekistan has historically developed faster than the organized one, which is due to less stringent regulatory requirements and a high share of privatization transactions [5].

The analysis of the legal framework presented in the study of A. Makhkamov demonstrates that the existing laws and regulations require a comprehensive reform. Special attention is paid to the regulation of the issuance and circulation of securities, as well as the protection of investors' rights. Scientific publications note that in order to increase the liquidity of the market, it is necessary to create more attractive conditions for public offering of shares (IPO) and expand the list of available investment instruments [6].

Foreign studies, such as the works of Y. Nishimura and D. Sornett, consider models of stock market functioning, including the impact of digital technologies on trading and clearing processes [7]. These studies demonstrate that the introduction of modern technologies, such as blockchain and algorithmic trading, contributes to increasing the efficiency of securities transactions [8].

Dynamics of the development of the market of organized and unorganized securities

The development of the securities market in Uzbekistan is characterized by significant differences between the organized and unorganized markets. Despite active efforts to form and develop an organized market, its share in the overall structure of the securities market remains low. This part of the article examines the dynamics of changes in both market segments, as well as the structure of trading, which have a significant impact on the efficiency of the stock market.

Dynamics of the development of the market of organized and unorganized securities. In recent years, Uzbekistan has seen an increase in trading volumes on the stock market, but the unorganized market continues to dominate. This is due to a number of factors, including less stringent requirements for participants, as well as the lack of high transaction costs typical of organized markets.

As shown in the studies, the volume of trade in the organized market in Uzbekistan is much lower compared to the unorganized one, which is confirmed by statistical data. For example, in 2020, the volume of stock trading in the organized market amounted to only 400.8 billion soums, which was only 0.17% of the total market volume, while the unorganized market showed much higher turnover (about \$7.1 billion). This indicates significant problems in the organization and development of the stock market infrastructure. One of the reasons for such disproportions is the imperfection of legislation and insufficient transparency in the organized market. In an unorganized market, participants regulate their transactions more freely, which makes it attractive for small and medium-sized businesses. However, from the point of view of long-term investments, the organized market offers a higher degree of protection of investors' rights, which requires further development and improvement.

Structure of trading on the stock market. The structure of trading on the stock market of Uzbekistan includes several key elements that form the dynamics of the development of this market segment. The most important aspect is the ratio of the primary and secondary stock markets.

Research and methods.

The primary securities market is a market where issuers (joint-stock companies) offer their securities for the first public offering (IPO). This market is an important mechanism for raising capital for companies. Over the past years, Uzbekistan has carried out several large placements of shares, but the IPO and SPO (secondary public offering) market remains limited.

In 2020, the volume of primary trading amounted to 748.9 billion soums, which amounted to 82.3% of the total trading volume on the stock market, which shows the significant interest of investors in primary placements. However, it is worth noting that until 2018, the share of the primary market was much lower, and there was a steady trend towards an increase in the number of placements every year. This is due to the improvement of the financial transparency of joint-

stock companies, as well as the government's actions to support the capitalization of large companies.

The secondary securities market is a market where investors buy and sell securities that have already been issued. Most of the trading takes place in this market, and it is in the secondary market that investors exercise their rights to shares and bonds.

The dynamics of the secondary market in Uzbekistan shows significant fluctuations. In 2019, the trading volume in the secondary market amounted to 839 billion soums, which amounted to 42.2% of the total trading volume. However, in 2020, this figure decreased significantly to 161.5 billion soums, or 17.7% of the total. This decline is due to the COVID-19 pandemic and uncertainty in the financial markets, which in turn affected investor interest in trading in the secondary market.

Despite these fluctuations, the secondary market continues to be an important element of the financial system. In particular, it serves as an indicator of market liquidity and plays a key role in assessing the value of companies based on market quotes. In Uzbekistan, the secondary market has a huge potential for growth, especially given the possible development of infrastructure and the improvement of legislative regulations.

The main participants of the stock market are commercial banks, investment companies, brokers and dealers, as well as individuals and legal entities that are investors. The market also includes government agencies that regulate and control the activities of market participants. The success of an organized market depends on coordinating the activities of all these participants and ensuring the transparency of trading.

In addition, an important aspect is the active participation of foreign investors, which largely depends on the level of confidence in the stock market of Uzbekistan and the availability of competitive financial instruments.

Problems and solutions

The main problems in the structure of trading on the stock market are:

- Low liquidity of the organized market, which makes it difficult for investors to make quick and profitable trades.
- Lack of a variety of financial instruments, such as government bonds or highly liquid corporate shares, which reduces the attractiveness of the market for large investors.
- The need to improve the digitalization of trade operations to ensure accessibility and convenience for all participants.
- Lack of specialized financial institutions, such as transfer agencies, which reduces the efficiency of securities transactions.

To address these challenges, it is necessary to continue reforming the financial infrastructure, develop digital platforms for trade, improve the regulatory framework, and attract more foreign and large domestic investors.

Share of joint-stock companies in the issue and turnover of securities

Joint-stock companies (JSC) play a key role in the securities market, providing a significant part of the issue and turnover. The issue of shares is the main way to raise capital for business development, improve financial condition and expand production capacity. In Uzbekistan, joint-stock companies make up a significant share in the structure of the stock market, but their participation in this process remains limited.

The main problem is the insufficient activity of joint-stock companies in the issue of new securities, which affects the size of the stock market. Despite positive changes in legislation and improved corporate governance, joint-stock companies often limit themselves to internal financing or turn to traditional sources of lending, which reduces the attractiveness of public offerings (IPOs).

In addition, the presence of joint-stock companies in the stock market of Uzbekistan is limited. For example, most large enterprises still do not consider the stock market as the main way to raise capital. This leads to an imbalance between the trading volume in the organized market and the unorganized market, where stock trading is less transparent and requires more control. Nevertheless, the role of joint-stock companies in the circulation of securities continues to grow. In 2019, there was an increase in secondary placements, which indicates an increase in interest in investing in equities, but this is still not enough to create a full-fledged stock market system.

Results.

Problems of the stock market functioning

The stock market of Uzbekistan faces a number of problems that significantly hinder its development. One of these problems is low liquidity, which is a consequence of the lack of involvement of large investors, as well as a limited number of financial instruments on the market. Liquidity plays a key role in assessing the attractiveness of the market for long-term and short-term investors. In conditions of low liquidity, shares and bonds cannot be quickly sold without significant losses, which scares off potential participants.

Another important aspect is the legal barriers that arise due to the imperfection of legislation. In Uzbekistan, mechanisms for protecting the rights of investors are still underdeveloped, especially in terms of transparency of tenders and the adequacy of regulation. Problems with the legal system, including unclear laws and lack of sufficient regulatory oversight, create conditions for market manipulation and reduce investor confidence.

Particular attention should be paid to the weak protection of shareholders' rights. In the context of insufficient protection of the interests of minority shareholders and insufficient information about the activities of companies, investors may face the risks of losing funds. The institution of corporate governance is not sufficiently developed in the stock market, which makes it difficult to attract long-term investments. Problems with information disclosure, non-compliance of corporate standards with international requirements and weak control over the activities of joint-stock companies do not help attract foreign investors, who are the main source of capital for emerging markets.

In addition, the stock market lacks sufficient infrastructure to improve listing mechanisms, as well as to create and manage highly liquid financial instruments, which also hinders the normal functioning of the stock market.

Thus, in order to improve the efficiency of the stock market in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to solve several key problems. The most important measures are the development of the legal framework, increasing market liquidity, improving the protection of investors' rights and creating conditions for the development of corporate governance in joint-stock companies.

Main Directions for Improving Securities Transactions in JSCs

One of the key areas for improving securities transactions in joint-stock companies is the improvement of the legislative and regulatory framework that meets modern requirements. To date, the legal framework governing the securities market in Uzbekistan has not yet been fully integrated with international standards. This creates barriers to the development of the market, and also limits the possibilities of attracting foreign investors. It is important to amend legislation that will ensure more transparent and predictable rules for the issuance, circulation and sale of securities, as well as improve the protection of investors' rights. The introduction of international standards, such as the principles of IOSCO (International Organization of Securities Commissions), will increase confidence on the part of both local and foreign market participants.

An equally important aspect is the development and improvement of listing mechanisms on the stock exchange. To do this, it is necessary to create more attractive conditions for companies that want to conduct an initial public offering (IPO). It is important to introduce new listing categories, such as "premium" and "standard", which will allow more joint-stock companies to register on the

stock exchange and raise capital. This will not only improve the capitalization of companies, but also increase the liquidity of the market. It is also worth paying attention to the development of the mechanism of secondary public offerings (SPOs), which will enable companies already operating in the market to raise additional capital without the need to conduct new IPOs.

The development of financial instruments and the expansion of the range of securities transactions also play a key role in improving the stock market. Currently, there is a limited number of investment instruments in the Uzbek market, which reduces the interest of large investors. The introduction of new instruments, such as corporate bonds, government bonds, derivatives and other derivative financial instruments, will significantly expand investment opportunities and increase the attractiveness of the market for large institutional investors. In addition, the development of digital financial technologies, including electronic trading platforms and blockchain, will ensure faster and more convenient transactions, increasing the efficiency and efficiency of securities transactions.

Finally, one of the most important tasks is to increase the level of corporate governance and improve the transparency of the activities of joint-stock companies. Creating effective mechanisms to protect the rights of minority shareholders, improving information disclosure and ensuring honesty in corporate reporting are prerequisites for attracting long-term investment. The introduction of mandatory corporate standards and regular audits of companies' activities will help increase investor confidence and ensure the long-term stability of the market. It is also important to establish a system of regular and timely informing investors about the financial results of companies, changes in their structure and strategic decisions, which will increase the level of confidence and transparency in the stock market.

Discussion.

Prospects and forecasts for the development of the securities market in joint-stock companies

The prospects for the development of the securities market in joint-stock companies of Uzbekistan in the coming years are associated with targeted efforts to modernize the financial infrastructure and improve the conditions for investment. In particular, with the development of the regulatory framework and the integration of Uzbekistan into the global financial system, an increase in interest in public offerings (IPOs) and an improvement in the dynamics of secondary trading are expected. In the long term, this should lead to a significant expansion of the issue of shares and an increase in turnover on the stock market, which will help to improve the liquidity and capitalization of joint-stock companies. It is predicted that the growth in the volume of transactions with securities will have a positive impact on the level of corporate investment and stimulate the development of infrastructure projects in the country.

One of the key tasks on the way to the development of the stock market is to increase the number of companies conducting IPOs. In the coming years, the Government of Uzbekistan plans to actively support initial public offerings of shares of large and medium-sized companies, which will lead to a significant increase in the number of joint-stock companies participating in the stock market. It is important that the development of this segment is not limited to state-owned enterprises. An increase in the number of private companies that will raise capital through the stock exchange is expected, which will make the market more diverse and stable. The introduction of new mechanisms, such as tax breaks for issuers and the reduction of barriers to entry will help stimulate this process.

Secondary trading in the stock market is also going to go through significant changes. It is expected to introduce modern trading technologies and improve the infrastructure for more efficient transactions. This will lead to increased liquidity and make the market more attractive to long-term investors. The introduction of digital technologies, such as blockchain and electronic platforms for securities trading, will create conditions for faster and safer transfer of assets. An important point will be the development of the secondary bond market, which can become an

important source of financing for government and corporate needs, as well as an attractive tool for investors.

We should also expect an increase in interest from international investors, especially if Uzbekistan continues to implement reforms in the field of finance and ensuring transparency in the stock market. In this regard, it is possible to integrate the Uzbek securities market with broader global financial flows. Attracting foreign investors will not only increase the volume of trade, but also increase confidence in the market, thus ensuring lower costs for raising capital for joint-stock companies.

Thus, the prospects for the development of the securities market in joint-stock companies of Uzbekistan are generally positive. In the coming years, we can expect a significant increase in both the number of issuers and trading volumes, an improvement in liquidity and an increase in the capitalization of companies. However, in order to achieve these goals, it is necessary to continue work on improving the legislative framework, developing financial technologies and strengthening the protection of investors' rights. As a result, the stock market will become an important tool for attracting investment and stimulating economic growth.

Conclusion.

The development of the securities market in joint-stock companies is an important element of economic growth, contributing to the attraction of capital, improving financial transparency and increasing the investment attractiveness of companies. In the course of the study, key aspects of the market functioning were considered, including the dynamics of the organized and unorganized segments, the structure of trading, the participation of joint-stock companies in the issue and circulation of securities, as well as the main problems limiting the development of the stock market.

The analysis showed that despite the measures taken, the stock market of Uzbekistan faces a number of serious challenges, such as low liquidity, legal barriers and weak protection of investors' rights. The lack of active participation of joint-stock companies in the stock market, insufficient infrastructure for IPOs and limited access to modern financial instruments hinder the inflow of investments and limit opportunities for effective redistribution of capital.

Improving securities transactions in joint-stock companies requires a comprehensive approach, including reforming the regulatory framework, introducing international regulatory standards, developing financial instruments and digital technologies, as well as strengthening mechanisms for protecting investors' rights. Improving corporate governance and increasing the transparency of corporate reporting will also be important factors in the growth of the stock market and increasing confidence from domestic and international investors.

Forecasts for the coming years suggest an expansion of trading volumes, the active introduction of modern technologies, an increase in the number of joint-stock companies entering IPOs, and an increase in interest from foreign investors. The implementation of these measures will create a more stable, liquid and competitive stock market, which will become an important tool for financing the long-term development of the economy of Uzbekistan.

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